

**make
a
thek**

**Deliverable D4.1
Personas and
Journey**

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
WP3	Mapping and Community Activation
WP4	Modular Makerspace Approach
WP5	Capacity Development
WP6	Community Engagement
WP7	European Public Library Pilots
WP8	Exploitation and Sustainability
WP9	CDO1 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 1)
WP10	CDO2 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 2)
WP11	Impact Assessment

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the user research carried out to define the ***make-a-thek personas and user journeys***, key tools for designing a modular makerspace approach tailored to public library contexts.

The work builds on **co-design methodologies and design thinking**, involving both library professionals and local communities across pilot countries. Research activities included interviews, online surveys, live workshops, and mapping exercises aimed at understanding needs, behaviours, barriers, and expectations related to making, fashion, craft, and circularity.

The outcome is a set of **multi-layered personas** (librarians, crafters, makers, citizens, circularity experts, fashion professionals, and prosumers), each paired with a detailed **narrative user journey**. These stories explore real-life interactions with makerspaces in public libraries, highlighting motivation, friction points, and engagement dynamics.

The findings provide crucial input for the **design of the *make-a-thek* toolkit** and its future implementation in pilot libraries, ensuring solutions that are inclusive, adaptable, and user-driven. In addition, these insights will inform subsequent Work Packages (WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7), guiding space configuration, training, facilitation, and community engagement strategies.

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the outcomes of Task 4.1, which focused on the development of the ***make-a-thek* User Personas and User Journeys**. These tools are fundamental in shaping the design and implementation of modular makerspaces within public libraries and other public spaces. Grounded in the principles of **local contextualisation**, the work draws from data collected from pilot libraries in WP3 and sets the foundation for designing adaptive, user-centred makerspace infrastructures in WP4 and beyond.

The personas and journeys described in this document serve to make visible the needs, motivations, skills, and barriers of current and potential users - ranging from library professionals and citizens to craftspeople and circularity practitioners. These insights ensure that the future *make-a-thek* environments will not only be technically equipped, but also socially and culturally responsive.

Project Context

The ***make-a-thek*** project aims to design and implement **modular, open, and inclusive makerspaces** in public libraries, to support **craft, fashion, and circular economy practices** across Europe. These spaces are conceived as accessible environments for experimenting, learning, producing, and sharing - where digital tools, traditional techniques, and community knowledge intersect.

Public libraries, with their trusted presence and community reach, are reimagined as hybrid cultural infrastructures: spaces where people can both access and co-create knowledge. The *make-a-thek* approach supports transformation by enabling local actors - whether experienced makers or curious citizens - to engage with **digital fabrication, reuse practices, and low-barrier craft experimentation**.

Task Overview - T4.1

Task 4.1 focused on the definition and development of ***make-a-thek* Personas and their related User Journeys**. It aimed to capture and visualise how different user groups - citizens, fashion and craft professionals, circularity experts, librarians, and prosumers - might interact with a *make-a-thek* makerspaces, with a *make-a-thek* toolkit, and what support they may require to fully benefit from them.

Building on user data collected in WP3 (T3.2), and including data collected in a series of preliminary co-design interviews, in person workshops, and observational studies and visits to *make-a-thek* pilot locations, the task clustered user characteristics and synthesised them into clear, representative personas.

These personas were then mapped against realistic journeys that highlight motivations, constraints, key touchpoints, emotions and engagement opportunities across different stages of interaction with *make-a-thek*.

The approach avoids stereotypes and aims to reflect real needs, goals, and contexts, also representing limit-situations, providing actionable insights for the design and customisation of spaces (T4.2), the mapping of skills needed (WP5), the planning of the pilot cities (WP7), future scaling recommendations (WP8) and beyond, to impact the overall project.

Deliverable Overview

This deliverable includes:

- A **methodology description**, outlining how user data was collected, analysed, and translated into design tools
- A set of ***make-a-thek* Personas** representing key user profiles across different contexts and expertise levels
- Associated **User Journeys** that explore how these personas engage with the makerspace ecosystem - from first contact to sustained participation
- **Key insights** for the design of adaptive makerspace environments, directly informing T4.2 “Designing the *make-a-thek* approach and its Modularity”

The content of this deliverable will directly feed into the **design and prototyping of the modular makerspace system**, supporting the customisation and scalability of the *make-a-thek* model across public libraries in Europe.

2. Methodology

2.1. Methodological Overview

The methodology adopted in Task 4.1 was grounded in a **design thinking¹, co-design² and user research³ approach**, aimed at developing a deep understanding of the diverse user groups that *make-a-thek* seeks to serve. The process was structured to centre the voices of both **library professionals** and **local communities**, ensuring that the resulting personas and user journeys are firmly rooted in real needs, expectations, and contexts.

¹ Interaction Design Foundation, “What is Design Thinking?”, Interaction Design Foundation, <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/design-thinking> (accessed October 31, 2025)

² Interaction Design Foundation, “Co-Design,” *Interaction Design Foundation*, <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/codesign> (accessed October 31, 2025)

³ Interaction Design Foundation, “What is User Research?”, *Interaction Design Foundation*, <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/user-research> (accessed October 31, 2025)

The research work was carried out through a series of iterative and participatory research activities involving the **pilot libraries** and their surrounding ecosystems. These included a cycle of one-on-one interviews with all participating pilot libraries, involving library directors, librarians directly engaged in the project, and - where relevant - public engagement officers, educators, and communication staff. All interviews were conducted online, allowing for consistency across countries while accommodating different institutional contexts.

In addition, where available, libraries provided access to previous audience research insights, as well as internal documentation on visioning, strategic planning, and spatial design. In several cases, **in-person field visits** were conducted by the project team, including **live interviews, photographic documentation, and spatial observations**, in order to better understand physical conditions and user flows.

Complementary data were also gathered through the **Community Activation** phase (WP3), which offered insight into local needs, goals, and community typologies. A dedicated **online form** was distributed across the network of pilot communities - targeting librarians, users, citizens, makers, and designers - to collect anonymized **qualitative data** on daily and professional use of creative spaces, including both library and non-library settings. These helped identify common use **patterns, expectations, and points of friction**.

Live **co-design sessions** were also conducted with representatives from all pilot libraries. During these sessions, participants were invited to **validate the user personas** developed on the basis of prior interviews with them. Building on this, they contributed to the development of user journeys by discussing key aspects to inform the *make-a-thek* approach, including: identifying minimum requirements for each library profile, defining the possible roles of librarians in supporting activities, mapping perceived barriers, and proposing how the *make-a-thek* toolkit could offer support - in terms of formats, tools, or resources (e.g., guides, templates, digital solutions).

In addition to the sessions with pilot library representatives, **live co-design sessions were also carried out with other relevant user groups** - including makers, designers, citizens, and library users. These took place during key pilot events (such as the FAB25⁴ event and the Barcelona Design Week - Distributed Design Conference “*Making (in) Commons*”⁵), and focused on exploring the spatial and material dimensions of the makerspaces. These moments allowed for the inclusion of diverse perspectives and hands-on contributions in shaping the *make-a-thek*

⁴ FAB25 Czechia, “The Future of Circular Library / Makerspaces,” *FAB25 Czechia – Program Schedule*, <https://fab25.fabevent.org/programs/schedule?day=2025-07-09&title=the-future-of-circular-library-makerspaces&event=6912c404-cbe8-4483-abe7-9dfe29f641c0> (accessed October 31, 2025)

⁵ Fab Lab Barcelona, “Making (in) Commons – Distribute Design,” *Fab Lab Barcelona*, <https://fablabbcn.org/calendar/conference-making-in-commons-distribute-design> (accessed October 31, 2025)

ecosystem. Table 01 below summarises the activities according to stakeholders and the main method of engagement used.

Activity Type	Stakeholders Involved	Method	Notes
Interviews	Library directors, librarians, educators, comms experts	Online (Google Meet)	8 interviews, 17 interviewees (Antwerp, Helsinki, Barcelona, Kranj, Budapest, Berlin, Reykjavik)
Field visits and interviews	Library staff (pilots)	On site	6 locations (Antwerp, Milan, Barcelona, Berlin, Opole, Reykjavik)
Community Activations	Citizens, library users, makers, designers, creatives	On site events and workshops	12 events - 210 participants
Survey	Broad audience	Online form (Google)	42 responses
Co-design session	Library staff (pilots)	On site in Reykiavik	29 participants Topic: all aspects + Library levels
Co-design session	Makers and designers	On site at FAB25 event	Topic: spaces and materials
Co-design session	Makers, designers, citizens and library users	On site at Barcelona pilot	Topic: spaces and materials
Co-design session	Library staff (pilots)	Online (Google meet)	15 participants Topic: all aspects + Library levels

Table 01: Research Activities - *make-a-thek* approach

Findings were synthesised into user personas and user journeys - narrative-based tools that reflect real experiences, behaviours, best practices, needs, challenges, barriers and opportunities across different user types that could be directly explored within the pilots contexts and beyond.

The user personas were subsequently **validated** by consortium members, each contributing feedback based on their specific **field of expertise and local context knowledge**.

These personas and journeys, described in the following chapters, form the backbone of the user-centred design strategy for *make-a-thek*.

2.2. Design Thinking and Co-design Process

The process followed the core principles of **human-centred design and participatory design**, moving through the phases of **empathise, define, ideate**, and **synthesise (sense making)**, with the goal of generating tools (personas and journeys) that would inform the design of inclusive and modular makerspaces.

Key steps included:

- **Empathising with users** through interviews and direct engagement
- **Defining needs and barriers** by clustering insights from diverse data sources
- **Ideating personas and journeys** through collaborative analysis with project partners and pilot actors
- **Verify the personas and journeys** with pilots and experts
- **Synthesising results** into the final actionable tools to inform space and service design in subsequent tasks (T4.2 and T4.3)

The methodology placed strong emphasis on **inclusion** and **local contextualisation**, seeking to reflect the realities of users from different geographies, backgrounds, and levels of familiarity with making and circular practices.

Stakeholder Engagement

To ensure both depth and diversity of insight, the research engaged with multiple stakeholder groups through a combination of methods, including desk research, semi-structured interviews, online surveys, and co-design sessions (see Chapter 2. Methodology). These activities involved:

- **Library managers and staff:** to understand institutional goals, current capabilities, and organisational barriers, through interviews and in person co-design meetings
- **Community managers and educators/facilitators:** to map ongoing collaborations and understand how community activation is already happening in different contexts, through interviews and in person co-design meetings
- **Existing and potential users of library spaces:** including local residents, hobbyists, crafters, makers, designers, fashion experts, students, parents, and underrepresented groups, through interviews and in person community activations meetings

2.3 Data collection

Data collection methods included:

- ❖ **Desk research** aimed at informing the design team and enriching the design sensibility around advanced makerspaces and hybrid cultural infrastructures in Europe. Although the activity was not structured as a formal comparative analysis and did not generate codified insights, it served an educational purpose for the personas and user journeys development. The research explored examples of modular design, community-driven practices, and sustainability-oriented programming.
- ❖ **Online forms** and surveys, distributed through library networks, collecting both quantitative and qualitative inputs
- ❖ **In-depth interviews** with *make-a-thek* pilot libraries directors, librarians, and programme coordinators across Europe
- ❖ **Live co-design sessions** with communities in the pilot locations, and with librarians in a focus on meeting, aimed at surfacing expectations, desires, concerns, and practical needs

3. Focus Areas and thematics

The research conducted in Task 4.1 was structured around key thematic areas, which emerged as fundamental to the development of the *make-a-thek* approach.

These thematic areas are the result of a careful **mapping of the key factors that will influence the design and implementation of the modular *make-a-thek* approach**. They reflect both **strategic** and **operational** dimensions - ranging from

space and technology to community engagement and cultural heritage - and provide a foundation for the next steps of the project.

Fig.01: Concept Map – Key Elements for the *make-a-thek* Modular Approach

Each of these areas will be further developed and operationalised in the subsequent tasks of WP4 and beyond, contributing to a flexible, context-aware, and inclusive makerspace model for public libraries.

These focus areas ensured that both the **strategic vision** and the **practical design elements** of the modular makerspaces would respond to real needs, diverse contexts, and systemic opportunities across the pilot sites.

The focus areas were:

- **Vision of the *make-a-thek* Approach**

We worked collaboratively with library teams and local communities to co-develop a shared understanding of what *make-a-thek* could become - its purpose, values, target audiences, expectations and long-term impact. This involved exploring different interpretations of what a public makerspace should offer and how it complements or expands the mission of the library.

In some cases, such as the Italian pilot (Milan - Community Activation Event), this research process led to a broader reflection on the future vision and

evolving role of public libraries. Participants collectively explored how libraries can be reimagined as hybrid infrastructures - places not only for accessing knowledge, but also for creative and sustainable experimentation, hands-on learning, and the development of new personal and professional skills. This redefinition of identity underscores the transformative potential of *make-a-thek*: to contribute to a wider shift in how libraries engage with their communities and respond to contemporary challenges.

Fig.02: Vision Board - *translated* - Milan Community Activation, July 2025

Key insights emerged regarding the Vision of the *make-a-thek* approach:

- Importance of defining the *make-a-thek* space not as a service, but as a shared learning environment. **The presence of machines and space alone does not create a makerspace**; rather, what matters is how the space **invites experimentation and fosters a "learning by doing" culture**.
- Spaces should be **familiar, accessible, and not intimidating**, with a clear purpose that avoids the perception of being overly technical or expert-only.
- Users should not expect staff to “do things for them” - instead, **library professionals should be seen as facilitators and co-learners**, supporting exploration with a “**we’ll Google it together**” attitude.
- So, **managing expectations** from the start is essential: a *make-a-thek* space is not a professional service but an opportunity for people to learn new skills, collaborate, and grow confidence through hands-on practice.

- **Machines and Materials**

Mapping existing and desirable digital fabrication tools as well as analogue equipment and physical materials. The aim was to define scalable and locally adaptable configurations that balance accessibility, creativity, and sustainability - while supporting circular making practices.

Key insights emerged regarding the Machines and Materials:

- **New machine acquisitions should be carefully evaluated** and only considered once there is clear evidence of community interest and the library's ability to manage them effectively. This includes assessing staff skills, available facilitation capacity, and the potential to design meaningful activities around the equipment rather than letting it remain underused.
- To promote user autonomy, **clear and accessible instructions** should accompany each machine, ideally supported by an **easy-to-update instruction system** - including visual guides, safety information, and simple templates for communication.
- Importance of a **dedicated calendar** to manage reservations, training sessions, workshops, and machine maintenance to improve efficiency and resource sharing.
- Participants emphasized the value of a **physical material gallery** - a tactile, on-site display allowing users to understand materials directly, supported by **basic guidelines on what can be made with each material**.
- Sustainability emerged as a key concern: we suggest **collaborations with circular centres, plans for reusing or redistributing leftover materials**, and guidance on when and how to monitor sustainability practices.
- Maintenance and safety are central topics, registering the need of **standard templates and booklets** to track revisions, repairs, and safety procedures.
- **Visual galleries (physical, digital) of upcycled garment examples** are recommended to inspire users, along with ready-to-use communication templates to explain materials, techniques, and possibilities in a simple, engaging way.

- **Spaces**

Exploring how makerspaces can be embedded in existing library environments, including the spatial constraints and opportunities of each pilot site. Attention was given to issues of visibility, openness, sound, modularity, security and coexistence between quiet zones and active making.

Key insights emerged regarding the Spaces:

- **Spaces should feel open, approachable, and familiar**, not intimidating or overly technical. They must clearly communicate their intended purpose and invite experimentation.
- **Multiple layout configurations** are needed - for example, one for open events and another for everyday autonomous use.
- **Accessibility** (physical access, inclusive design) must be considered from the start.
- **Noise management** strategies should be in place, particularly when making activities coexist with quiet library zones.
- **Dedicated storage areas** are needed for personal and shared materials.
- Spaces can be enriched through **collaborations with local manufacturing partners, fab labs, and makerspaces**, enabling access to tools, know-how, and production capacity. Sourcing reused or sustainable materials through these networks can also reinforce the circular ethos of the *make-a-thek* approach and support local economies.
- **Space set-up:** ventilation must be ensured, especially for equipment that produces fumes or heat; adequate energy supply and sockets are essential for flexibility and safety; safety considerations should guide space planning and machine use.
- **Instructions and best practices for setting up and managing spaces could be shared between libraries (peer-to-peer support)** to support replication and scalability.

- **Craft, Local Culture and Heritage / Activities**

Understanding local craft and fashion heritages - both traditional and contemporary - and how they can be meaningfully connected to the makerspace activities. This also included mapping ongoing practices such as textile reuse, jewellery making, ceramics, knitting, and how these could evolve through digital and circular innovation.

Key insights emerged regarding the Activities:

- Staff needs **time, tools, and internal clarity** to implement activities effectively.
- Defining a clear **vision and strategic planning** for activities and their role in the broader mission of the library can help to align the team, ensure support and coordination, and communicate with intentions to the users.
- Designing activity formats with **consistency** and organising **regular workshops (“adopt new rituals” approach)** or session series tailored to specific audiences or themes could help to align the programme with the library’s evolving identity as a community and creative hub.
- **Facilitation** roles are crucial: at least one person (librarian or external expert) should act as host/facilitator during activities to welcome participants, guide the session, and maintain an inclusive atmosphere. Involving external facilitators and experts to enrich the programme can be a key factor.
- Developing **partnership** agreements and joint communication strategies helps to ensure continuity and clarity. A “networker” figure within the library staff could be needed to engage with partners, foster community activities, and represent the library externally.
- A **clear schedule and communication plan** (both internal and external) is key to coordination.
- The use of **templates for reports** and evaluations can help ensure that learnings are captured and activities continuously improved.
- Collecting and sharing **best practices** within the *make-a-thek* network serve as inspiration and support for future initiatives. Activities formats could be needed for the beginner libraries.

- **Communities and User engagement**

Identifying key user groups and community actors who are (or could be) engaged with the makerspace. This involved examining current forms of participation in library events, informal networks of makers and creatives, and community-led practices that could be integrated or supported within the *make-a-thek* ecosystem.

Key insights emerged regarding the Communities and User engagement:

- It's needed to understand and connect with the community: collect qualitative and quantitative data on the communities involved can help to design relevant activities. A **community manager** is really recommended as well, by the most active libraries. Checklists with **guiding questions** could help to explore user needs and motivations.
- There could be the need to **diversify engagement strategies**, though tailored formats and approaches. Makers and designers are often underrepresented within the libraries communities - targeted outreach is needed to close this gap. Involve schools, researchers, and universities can activate intergenerational and interdisciplinary participation.
- **Promoting cross-community awareness by showcasing / exhibiting** what's happening in different neighbourhoods or groups is highlighted as best practice by the most active libraries.
- Many libraries are not systematically **mapping** their local communities or stakeholders. Guides and checklists can support local mapping efforts.
- Having **poster templates, branding and communication materials**, and a **checklist for event promotion** can make outreach more effective and consistent.

- **Skills and Competences**

Mapping both existing and needed skills across different user types - librarians, crafters, citizens, prosumers, experts. The focus was on identifying gaps in digital literacy, circular knowledge, facilitation, and peer learning, in order to inform future training, onboarding strategies, and educational resources (WP5, WP6).

Key insights emerged regarding the Skills and Competencies:

- Library staff should and would learn the **basics of each machine** available in the makerspace (e.g. how to turn it on, how it works, common uses), and ideally acquire basic maintenance skills to troubleshoot and extend the life of equipment.
- Having in-house know-how is more sustainable than relying on external facilitators only: this can be settled by establishing an **internal network of expertise** within the library team.
- Starting simple can be the key, encouraging step-by-step learning and avoiding overcomplicating early activities, and focusing on peer-to-peer learning to empower users to share knowledge and build a **collaborative learning culture**.
- Staff should act as **inspirers** rather than experts, being updated on trends, ideas, and projects to motivate users (cfr. Vision of the *make-a-thek* Approach).
- Seems fundamental to offer **practical directions**, not just theoretical instruction - show how to apply skills to real needs.

These focus areas acted as the analytical backbone for generating the *make-a-thek* personas and journeys, and will continue to inform the modular design of spaces and services in WP4 and WP5.

These key elements were also used to define a preliminary framework for the *make-a-thek* approach, aimed at developing **flexible implementation scenarios that reflect the different levels of experience and readiness of the pilot libraries** across each factor. This framework formed the basis for structuring a **multifactorial, progressive modularity model** - one that can adapt to diverse local capacities, contexts, and ambitions.

To better support pilot libraries in navigating this process, the concept of levels was further refined during internal discussions and co-design activities. A tiered approach was introduced to represent a pathway of **continuous improvement** across all core aspects of *make-a-thek* implementation.

The levels - beginner, intermediate, and advanced - are not fixed categories but dynamic stages that reflect a library's evolving relationship with its community, equipment, knowledge-sharing practices, and sustainability goals.

- ❖ At the **beginner level**, libraries start engaging communities using existing or low-barrier tools, testing new approaches, and learning alongside external experts.
- ❖ The **intermediate level** involves a stronger network presence, expanded infrastructure, peer-to-peer learning, and increased community ownership of the space.
- ❖ The **advanced level** envisions autonomous community engagement, deeper circular practices, advanced knowledge-sharing ecosystems, and strategies for maintaining long-term sustainability of the space.

This evolving structure helps set **clear expectations, baseline requirements, and tailored guidelines** for the pilot libraries, while providing a **flexible roadmap that supports iterative growth and adaptation over time.**

4. User Personas and User Journeys

4.1 Personas selection and definition

These personas represent diverse user profiles across the project's main target groups, and were carefully selected and developed to reflect real needs, behaviours, skills, and motivations, as well as to help anticipate barriers and opportunities for engagement.

As described in detail in the methodology section above, personas were co-defined through a combination of desk research, interviews, live community engagements, and local pilot interactions, using a design thinking and co-design methodology.

AIM: Each persona serves as a design tool to guide the shaping of spaces, tools, activities, and communication strategies within the *make-a-thek* ecosystem.

The selection aimed to **represent a diverse spectrum of roles and relationships with libraries and making practices, covering different levels of expertise, familiarity with circularity, and proximity to library services.** The personas are not

generic archetypes, but **context-specific profiles based on qualitative insights gathered in the pilot cities.**

The following categories of personas were developed in collaboration among project partners:

- librarians
- makers
- crafters
- fashion designers
- circularity experts
- prosumers
- citizens, both library users and non-users

Together, these personas contribute to building a nuanced understanding of the human dimension of the *make-a-thek* approach and will inform the following stages of design and implementation.

Particularly crucial are the **librarian profiles, as the digital kit is primarily addressed to them and their institutions** - making their needs, motivations, and barriers essential for shaping an effective and usable tool.

It was felt essential to design **site-specific personas** representing the pilot libraries, in order to capture the unique local needs, challenges, and conditions shaping their engagement with the *make-a-thek* approach. To represent the impact of *make-a-thek* through realistic personas, both typical and edge-case scenarios were outlined - including, for example, individuals who are initially reluctant or sceptical about the introduction of a makerspace within a library context. This, combined with the wide variety of potential users and the different motivations and goals each of them may have, explains the high number of personas developed. For examples, given the specific political and social context, dedicated personas and user journeys were developed to reflect the experiences and needs of Ukrainian individuals in a respectful and context-sensitive manner.

The decision to represent such a broad spectrum was intentional, aiming to reflect the social and cultural diversity across contexts - where people's behaviours, expectations, and engagement with makerspaces can vary significantly.

All personas are presented in detail in chapter 4.4 - Users Personas and Journeys - TABLES

4.2 User Journeys narrative structure

The user journeys developed in this task adopt a **narrative and temporal structure**, designed to bring forward not only what users do, but how they feel, reflect, and

grow in their interaction with the *make-a-thek* makerspace and its related services. Each journey is articulated in four evolving phases: **Examine**, **Elect**, **Evaluate**, and **Entrust** (see chapter 4.3 - Structure and how to read them).

This episodic format helps capture how users progressively engage with the space - from early exposure or accidental discovery (Examine), to initial participation (Elect), critical reflection (Evaluate), and long-term commitment (Entrust). The narrative approach makes visible not just functional touchpoints, but also **emotional shifts, social dynamics, and latent needs**, giving depth to user experience and context to behavioural patterns.

A key focus of this structure is to highlight **pain points, barriers, and moments of friction**, whether related to physical access, confidence in using equipment, alignment with personal values, or challenges in navigating the makerspace environment or digital tools. These include both the experience within the library setting and potential frictions in interacting with the **make-a-thek toolkit** (e.g. unclear entry points, lack of facilitation, limited personalisation, etc.).

By embedding these lived dynamics into storytelling, the journeys offer **rich, user-grounded insights** that are actionable for design. They help ensure that the *make-a-thek* modular approach, tools, and services are not only inclusive and adaptable, but also resonate with the real trajectories, capacities, and motivations of diverse communities. Moreover, this work informs the development of other WPs - particularly WP4, WP5 and WP7 - by anchoring design criteria in an authentic and useful user experience.

4.3 Structure and how to read them

Each **User Persona** is presented through a standard format that includes:

Profile information: Name, age range, role, residence, and a short quote expressing their values or point of view.

Background: A narrative summary of their experience and position in relation to making, fashion/craft, circularity, and/or library use.

Skill levels: Visual indicators of their literacy in areas such as digital fabrication, circularity & reuse, and fashion or craft expertise. This section aims to represent the general literacy level of each individual, rather than providing an exhaustive overview of specific skills and experiences. For this reason, the fashion and craft areas have not been distinguished at this stage; they will be addressed later, during the development of the toolkit in T4.2 and WP5, with a more analytical and sector-specific approach.

Use of the service: Divided into four sections - **Behaviour, Goals, Needs, and Barriers** - to identify what they seek, what they value, and what may limit their engagement. The section 'Behaviour' also includes details about the communities the persona can be involved in.

To support clarity and differentiation across the various user types, a set of **tags** has been introduced in the visualization (e.g. same target, different role), helping to classify the personas and better reflect the diversity of approaches, expertise, functions and goals within each category.

Each **user journey** is structured as a short narrative that unfolds in four chronological and emotional stages:

Examine: The first contact with the makerspace - what triggers their interest or curiosity.

Elect: The moment they choose to engage - what motivates their participation and what they try first.

Evaluate: Their reflections - what works, what doesn't, and where they see value or limitations.

Entrust: The final stage - whether and how they become regular users, contributors, or advocates.

This structure allows each persona to be more than a fixed profile: it becomes a story in motion, showing how the *make-a-thek* could evolve alongside its users. It also reveals **key moments, emotional touchpoints, and barriers** that can be directly addressed in the design of the *make-a-thek* toolkit and the modular approach, as well as in communication, facilitation, and training strategies across the project.

4.4 User Personas and Journeys - TABLES

Julia

(she/her)

Librarian

Hobbyst

Library Level 1

"Kids think I'm fun; my accessories make them think I'm slightly magical... I love it!"

Residence: Barcelona

Age range: 43 y.o.

Role/attitude: librarian, studied pedagogy

background

Julia is a Spanish librarian with a background in pedagogy. She leads the Kids and Families section, where her creativity truly shines. The workshops she designs are always fun, original, and full of energy - just like her. With her expressive, ironic sense of humor, Julia knows exactly how to keep children engaged. Outside of work, she's a mom to a 10-year-old boy. She's also passionate about fashion and is rarely seen without her stylish, often handmade, accessories.

goal

Turn her passion into engaging, learning-based experiences as part of a career shift.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

She doesn't have expertise in that field.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

She carefully follows all library guidelines and loves giving new life to old garments and textiles when creating her own accessories.

FASHION & CRAFTS

She loves fashion, though she's not a designer, and enjoys creating her own accessories.

behaviour

Julia has been working at the library for eight years, mainly in the children's department, where her creative workshops for families have become a great success. About a year ago, the library, inspired by the M-A-T toolkit, set up a makerspace with tables, tools, and computers—but no activities were launched. More recently, three sewing machines were donated by a local women's association that was upgrading its equipment. The management asked Julia—who already enjoys making her own accessories—to come up with a series of workshops for young adults on customized creations, possibly in collaboration with the women from the association. Although it was outside her usual role, Julia embraced the challenge with enthusiasm.

needs

- Guidance, structure and listening from top managers
- Skills growth to lead new activities/machines and on people management (ex: ability to propose technical activities for unexperienced participants)
- Foster new community connections (associations)
- Adapt her hobby to a structured series of activities
- Sufficient and engaged personnel to support her
- Continuous training
- Resources:
 - time to balance her regular responsibility and the new activity
 - sourcing of materials

barriers

- Limited experience with the new target
- Not enough media experience for event promotion
- Lack of formal training (safety, managing equipment)
- Extra hours required by the new activities - potential conflict with personal life
- Risk of burnout - to prevent her passion from turning into an unwanted obligation.

Julia's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Julia was already aware that the library had adopted the make-a-thek toolkit, but until now, only limited resources had been dedicated to it. With the recent donation of sewing machines, management saw a chance to truly invest in the makerspace. For Julia, the machines felt like a bridge between her personal passion for making accessories and her professional experience in designing workshops. Eager to contribute, she began browsing the toolkit, looking for case studies from libraries with similar profiles and challenges. She imagined how the space could evolve - but quickly realized that without proper technical skills, her ideas might remain just that: ideas. She considered signing up for an introductory course on using the machines, hoping to build confidence and avoid relying solely on trial and error. She also needed time to do her own research, but wasn't sure where to begin. At the same time, she counted on the support of her colleagues, expecting a cohesive team effort. In reality, communication was sometimes fragmented, and roles were not clearly defined. Julia's excitement filled her with energy, fueling a wave of creative ideas. Her enthusiasm helped her imagine bold directions for the space, even if the road ahead held many unknowns - from technical hurdles to scheduling challenges. This optimistic momentum became a driving force, encouraging her to dive in, experiment, and learn by doing, even in the face of complexity

ELECT

Motivated by this potential, Julia decided to take the lead. She proposed a series of beginner-friendly workshops on customized accessories, possibly in collaboration with the women's association that had donated the sewing machines - inviting them to help plan and facilitate the sessions. With management's approval, she turned to the m-a-t toolkit for guidance, using it to outline the steps for her first event: shaping the activities, drafting simple learning materials, and preparing a communication plan through the library's existing channels. Balancing this new role with her ongoing responsibilities in the Kids' department, however, required careful time management. Julia found herself needing clearer task organization and dedicated moments for breaks and preparation. Ideally, some of her regular duties could be covered by colleagues - freeing up just enough space to focus on the makerspace initiative. As the event approached, she also felt the pressure of community expectations. Promoting something new meant not only reaching the right audience, but also proving its value. Still, Julia remained energized by the opportunity to bring something fresh and creative to the library, and to see how people might respond.

EVALUATE

After running her first workshops, Julia began collecting feedback from participants through informal conversations and short surveys. She noticed strong enthusiasm for hands-on customization, especially when participants could bring their own garments and ideas. At the same time, some activities - like basic sewing techniques - proved too advanced for beginners, or too difficult for her to facilitate confidently. Julia realized that interpreting feedback isn't always straightforward. She started looking for effective ways to understand what truly resonated, how to keep people engaged over time, and how to make sure future sessions reflect the diverse needs of the community across age groups, skill levels, and cultural backgrounds. She hopes to compare her experience with examples from other m-a-t libraries, drawing inspiration and identifying good practices. This would help her refine both the structure and content of the workshops, while also offering management solid evidence of the project's potential and the value it brings to the community.

ENTRUST

Encouraged by the positive response, the library decided to integrate sewing and textile workshops into its long-term strategy. This shift gave Julia the confidence to take the next step: opening the space to broader collaboration and experimentation. She began reaching out to local creatives, associations, and small businesses, inviting them to propose ideas, share skills, or donate second-hand materials. While the enthusiasm was high, Julia soon realized that building partnerships takes time, trust, and the right alignment of interests. Formal agreements, funding proposals, and sponsorship discussions often extended beyond her role - requiring support from project managers or administration. Still, she played a key role in making the space welcoming for collaborators, acting as a connector and host for freelance experts or guest facilitators. With continued support from the make-a-thek community, Julia helped shape the makerspace into a creative hub where personal passions, circular values, and community learning could grow side by side.

Jess

(they/them)

Librarian

Skilled

Library level II

"We are all different, like the cups in my kitchen."

Residence: Eindhoven

Age range: 35 y.o.

Role/attitude: librarian, previously designer

background

Jess is a Belgian designer by training. They recently moved to the Netherlands with their sister and decided to change careers to work in a library. They were hired for their past experience and confidence in digital fabrication. At home, Jess is busy renovating their new apartment, giving old furniture a second life and customizing it.

Their favorite pastime? Reading a book with a cup of tea and a slice of cheesecake.

goal

Contributing their skills to their new workplace

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Thanks to their past experience, they have strong expertise in facilitating user activities and working with digital tools.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Strong interest in giving a second life to things and regenerative design of products.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Experience in craft. Not much in fashion - could have difficulty to generate ideas to offer to users

behaviour

Jess is relatively new to working in a library environment. At present, the library does not have dedicated community groups to collaborate with or propose activities to. Nevertheless, Jess's expertise makes them well-suited to independently organize initiatives - such as reaching out to local associations or facilitating workshops.

The library currently owns only a single 3D printer, and none of the librarians know how to use it. Jess sees great potential in transforming the library into a true makerspace, where citizens could acquire new skills, bring their ideas to life (as Jess has done in their own apartment), or simply enjoy creative activities in their free time.

Jess's wide network of contacts across Europe could also play a key role in enriching the library's program by involving visiting experts and proposing relevant activities.

needs

- Growth in the library context
- Resources and infrastructures
- Social belonging and local integration
- Community engagement opportunities
- Learn how to design a service

barriers

- Lack of knowledge about the territory, and language barriers (but could bring also new people from the origin country)
- Lack of skills as facilitator, especially to beginners
- Limited resources available to launch activities/events
- Colleagues who have different perspectives and are reluctant to change.
- Difficulty engaging local people interested in making
- Difficulties to relate with different library users; not used to work with public.

Jess' Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

A former colleague of Jess, aware of their career shift into more community-oriented and circular fashion practices, shares a link to the make-a-thek project, suggesting it could be a meaningful opportunity. Intrigued, Jess signs up for the newsletter and begins browsing the toolkit. As they explore case studies and examples from other libraries, something clicks - this doesn't feel like another top-down initiative, but something practical and close to their values. They feel, "this is for you." Yet, the excitement is mixed with uncertainty. Jess wonders: "Does my project really fit here?". The toolkit is rich, but they wish someone could walk them through the first steps. They get stuck on what to do next and feel the absence of a real person to contact. Without clear, accessible entry points, Jess considers giving up. The potential is there, but the onboarding feels like a lonely path. However, the kit present a clear path, and they see how it supports libraries in strengthening makerspaces, review case studies from other institutions, and start to imagine how it might fit their own library's future vision.

ELECT

Determined not to lose momentum, Jess decides to pitch the make-a-thek opportunity to a library management. They highlight how the toolkit could help upskill the makerspace already present in the library, both in terms of equipment and programming, and in terms of evolving the vision of the library itself. The management agrees to a trial, suggesting a one-off event to test the waters. With support from a couple of colleagues familiar with the community, Jess begins shaping the event. They use the toolkit's basic planning guide, with "IKEA-style" templates - step-by-step blueprints clear also for non-designers. Promotion is another challenge: the event needs visibility, and Jess lacks communication support. They improvise with a newsletter post and word-of-mouth, but some key "ingredients" for the perfect event still feel missing - like targeted outreach or graphics to attract the right audience. There's a sense of doing everything manually, with not enough backup.

EVALUATE

The pilot event draws 7 participants. Small, but engaged. Jess interviews attendees, takes notes, and senses genuine interest, especially around textile reuse and skills-sharing. This feedback becomes the basis for a quick community survey, shared again via the newsletter. But results are underwhelming - few responses trickle in. Jess realizes that traditional communication channels aren't enough; people don't always read newsletters, and reaching potential users requires a more personal, grassroots approach. They're left wondering: What's the right way to collect useful feedback? What questions do we really need to ask? Despite these hurdles, the event proves valuable. Jess starts to build a clearer vision of what the makerspace could become, and how it might serve both the library and local creatives. The challenge now is transforming one good experience into a strategy.

ENTRUST

Encouraged by the positive responses, Jess pushes for make-a-thek to become part of the library's long-term strategy. Management agrees, and with that comes greater confidence. Jess starts leading new initiatives, now with support from a small internal team and inspiration from the broader network. They begin partnering with local makers and external experts, experimenting with circular activities

Daniel

(he/him)

Librarian

Library Level III

"We'll Google it together!"

Residence: Stavanger, Norway

Age range: 50-55 y.o.

Role/attitude: Senior librarian

background

Daniel is a senior librarian at the city library of Stavanger. He studied Cultural Heritage and began his career as a researcher. For the past 20 years, he has worked at the library, becoming the main expert on its book collections, book clubs, and literary events. Outside of work, Daniel dedicates his time to his urban garden and caring for plants in his apartment, a passion he shares with his son, who holds a PhD in Agriculture.

goal

use his expertise and network to engage diverse audiences and promote sustainable practices

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Daniel doesn't have experience in this area, but he knows how to support users in related activities.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Daniel adopts many sustainable habits in his personal life and is a leading advocate for making the library fully circular.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Daniel doesn't have experience in this area, but he knows how to support users in related activities.

behaviour

Daniel is a senior librarian at the Stavanger library, with decades of experience building strong community connections through book clubs, conferences, and writer events. While his role isn't directly tied to the makerspace, he has formal safety training and can guide users on how to use the equipment. As part of the management, he wants to help the makerspace engage a wider audience by leveraging his broad network to attract more participants. Passionate about sustainability, Daniel supports the makerspace by building connections with companies to reuse discarded materials and promote circular best practices in the space, ensuring that sustainability is considered in all the activities offered.

needs

- Engagement support: strategies and framework to reach, listen and involve different audiences with cultural and socio-economical sensitivity
- Basic knowledge of the machines, to understand the potential of the makerspace
- Sustainability resources and best practices
- Help from colleagues to manage the space
- Create opportunities through collaboration with external partners (levering his network)

barriers

- Limited hands-on experience with makerspace activities
- Challenging to engage diverse audiences (not usual ones)
- No clear structure for managing external partners
- Resources: time to balance his regular responsibility and the new supporting activity

Daniel's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Daniel notices that the library's makerspace is equipped with interesting tools and offers occasional workshops, but community engagement remains limited.

Curious and motivated by his interest in sustainability and community development, he begins to explore the m-a-t toolkit and reviews how other libraries have structured their makerspaces. He's particularly drawn to examples where diverse audiences have been successfully engaged, and where circularity practices are embedded in creative programming.

He starts imagining how his expertise in community building and facilitation could support the growth of the space — but also becomes aware of some personal and systemic gaps: his limited technical expertise with makerspace tools, and the lack of sufficient financial, technical, and network support to activate the kind of inclusive and sustainable initiatives he envisions.

ELECT

Seeing an opportunity to make a meaningful impact, Daniel decides to actively support the makerspace. He proposes to management strategies for engaging new audiences, leveraging his network of writers, local organizations, and community groups.

He also identifies potential partnerships with companies to supply second-hand materials and promote circular practices. With management approval, he prepares to guide the first initiatives and offer support during workshops, alongside an expert facilitator.

EVALUATE

Daniel observes the initial makerspace events, noting which activities draw the most interest and where participants struggle. He gathers feedback from attendees, evaluates the effectiveness of his engagement strategies, and identifies areas where additional guidance or resources are needed.

Comparing his experiences with other libraries, he refines approaches to participant outreach, sustainability practices, and collaboration with external partners.

ENTRUST

Confident from early successes, Daniel fully embraces his role supporting the makerspace. He continues leveraging his network to bring in participants, external experts, and sustainable materials.

He advocates for the integration of makerspace activities into the library's long-term strategy, shares best practices with colleagues, and positions the space as a hub for community learning, creativity, and sustainability.

Sonja

(she/her)

fashion designer

student

"I want to make clothes that are beautiful and responsible, but I don't even know where to start."

Residence: Lubiana, Slovenia

Age range: 28-35 y.o.

Role/attitude: Junior designer / working student in a fashion start-up.

background

Sonja is a 28-year-old junior designer, working at a fashion start-up. She is at the very beginning of her sustainability journey and has only a theoretical understanding of circular fashion. Highly motivated to learn, Sonja wants to explore upcycling and DIY methods to make her designs more responsible. In her studies, she has developed solid fashion knowledge and enjoys experimenting with crafts, but she needs concrete, practical foundations to integrate circularity into her work. Outside of work, Sonja is curious, social, and active online - often learning new techniques through tutorials and influencer content.

goal

Gain practical skills and confidence to create sustainable, circular fashion designs.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Minimal experience with digital tools; mostly self-taught experimentation.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Theoretical knowledge only

FASHION & CRAFTS

Strong fashion background and an experimental approach to crafts

behaviour

Sonja uses the makerspace as a playground for experimenting with materials and techniques she discovers online. She enjoys hands-on exploration and testing her ideas but benefits from structured examples and step-by-step guidance. She is active on social media, follows influencers, and learns through tutorials, which she often tries to replicate in the makerspace environment.

needs

- Practical, step-by-step guidance for starting circular design.
- Affordable sustainable or reusable materials for small projects.
- Workshops to learn upcycling and DIY techniques.
- Networking with experienced designers and artisans
- Test projects before launching them with her start-up
- Mentoring programme
- An inspiring, supportive community that values experimentation

barriers

- Limited budget and access to sustainable materials.
- Uncertainty and lack of confidence to begin.
- Few concrete examples or role models to follow.
- Limited institutional support for emerging designers.

Sonja's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Sonja is building her own fashion micro-brand, and comes across the library makerspace while watching sewing tutorials online. Curious to test her skills in a real setting, she signs up for a beginner workshop. As she steps into the space, she's shy but observant - taking in the layout, the people, the vibe. The idea of making alongside others feels both exciting and intimidating.

ELECT

She starts attending open sessions to refine her sewing skills and test designs using donated fabrics. After a few weeks, she feels confident enough to bring in her own materials and start prototyping small items. A facilitator notices her consistency and introduces her to others with similar interests, expanding her informal support network.

EVALUATE

Sonja loves the space, but faces challenges: limited opening hours clash with her part-time job, and it's not always easy to access quality materials. Still, the affordability and access to tools keep her coming back. She begins sharing her process online, tagging the makerspace in her posts and attracting a small following.

ENTRUST

Eventually, Sonja becomes a peer mentor - helping new participants feel welcome, giving mini-tutorials, and contributing to community resources. She begins shaping a toolkit for other young designers who, like her, want to start small, local, and sustainable.

Stefanie

(she/her)

fashion designer

entrepreneur

"Circular fashion is not just a trend; it's a responsibility. Every design choice can have a lasting impact on people and the planet."

Residence: Hamburg/Berlin, Germany

Age range: ~35–45

Role/attitude: Designer & founder, specializing in sustainable and circular fashion

background

Stefanie is a German designer and entrepreneur based between Hamburg and Berlin. With several years of experience in the fashion industry, she focuses on sustainable and circular fashion, particularly upcycling and socially driven projects. She is passionate about making circularity a standard practice, promoting sustainable materials, fair production processes, and mentoring emerging designers

behaviour

Stefanie collaborates with NGOs, start-ups, and makerspaces to integrate her projects into broader communities. She uses the makerspace as a laboratory to test innovative ideas, prototype sustainable designs, and host workshops to share her expertise. She actively seeks new sustainable materials and techniques, treating the makerspace both as a creative hub and a platform for education and collaboration.

goal

To prototype new circular fashion materials and methods in a real-world setting, using the library as a space for experimentation and public engagement. She seeks to share her skills while gathering feedback from diverse users, turning the makerspace into a place of exchange, dialogue, and collaborative innovation.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Familiar with digital tools for prototyping but not a technical expert.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Highly experienced in circular design, upcycling, and sustainable materials.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Expert fashion designer with strong craft skills and industry knowledge.

needs

- Affordable access to sustainable and innovative materials for prototyping.
- Collaboration opportunities with makers, designers, and community groups.
- A platform to share expertise through workshops and talks.
- Tools and machines that support design, prototyping, and material experimentation.
- A community that values sustainability and supports circular practices.

barriers

- High costs and limited availability of sustainable materials.
- Difficulty in gaining wider market acceptance for circular products.
- A need to raise awareness and overcome skepticism among consumers, brands, and potential partners.
- Time constraints balancing personal projects, collaborations, and mentoring roles.

Stefanie's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Stefanie hears about the library's makerspace through a local sustainability event. She decides to attend a session out of curiosity, not expecting much. However, as she steps into the space and sees community members upcycling old garments, she feels an immediate spark. The sewing machines, community feel, and openness to experimentation remind her of why she started working with textiles in the first place.

ELECT

Encouraged, Stefanie offers to run a small workshop on transforming old clothes into wearable accessories. She brings in some of her own fabric scraps and tools.

The response is overwhelmingly positive: participants of all ages share memories attached to garments, swap ideas, and experiment with stitching and dyeing. The energy feels raw but authentic, and Stefanie sees the potential not just for teaching, but for learning as well—gaining insight into how different people approach clothing, repair, and creativity.

EVALUATE

After a few sessions, Stefanie reflects on what's working and what isn't. While the atmosphere is vibrant, she finds herself limited by the availability of machines and materials. She also notices that participants need different levels of guidance.

Yet what keeps her coming back is the reciprocal value of the space: she learns new perspectives from people she wouldn't usually meet, finds inspiration in their questions and ideas, and is challenged to explain her techniques in simpler ways. It's a refreshing contrast to the fashion world's competitiveness and individualism.

ENTRUST

Over time, Stefanie becomes a trusted part of the community. She starts designing beginner-friendly guides and informally mentoring newer participants.

Rather than building her own permanent workshop, she sees the space as a living studio—a place to test new ideas and engage in ongoing dialogue with the public around fashion, waste, and inclusion. The makerspace becomes a shared environment for creative exchange, where her expertise grows in tandem with the community's voice.

Amira

(she/her)

Circularity expert

Environmental Engineer

"Cities are living ecosystems, circularity helps them thrive."

Residence:	Norway (experience in Lebanon and the Netherlands)
Age range:	40s
Role/attitude:	Circular economy consultant, systemic thinker, sustainability advocate

background

Amira studied Environmental Engineering at the American University of Beirut and completed a master's in Industrial Ecology and Circular Economy at TU Delft. She has lived and worked in Lebanon, the Netherlands, and Norway, focusing her career on policy advising, consulting, and research. She has over a decade of experience helping cities and organizations integrate circular practices and resilience thinking. Personally, she values low-impact living and local ecosystems, aligning her lifestyle with her professional ethos.

behaviour

Amira is a circular economy consultant who collaborates with municipalities, startups, and cultural institutions to transition towards circular urban systems. She brings systemic expertise in material flows and resource management and is motivated by the Fab City vision of shifting from PITO (Product-In/Trash-Out) to DIDO (Data-In/Data-Out). Amira sees makerspaces as living laboratories where circular strategies can be tested and communicated to citizens, even if she herself is not hands-on with machines.

goal

Use public events and workshops to raise awareness and inspire change - not only as a personal mission, but as part of a broader municipal or policy-driven strategy. Her work supports long-term sustainability goals, blending community engagement with institutional impact.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Limited hands-on experience

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Deep theoretical and strategic knowledge of circular economy practices and resource management.

FASHION & CRAFTS

No background in fashion and minimal practical crafting experience.

needs

- Pathways to connect her strategic knowledge to makerspace practices.
- Educational frameworks and participatory methods that make circular concepts accessible to diverse audiences.
- A framework for collaboration with institutions, companies, and grassroots groups.
- Access to local material flow data to design circular strategies that are grounded in place.

barriers

- Limited hands-on or technical skills in makerspace tools and processes.
- Risk of being seen as too abstract or strategic without concrete examples.
- Circular initiatives can face resistance due to cost, time, or complexity.
- Balancing consultancy work with community involvement.
- Making workshops and events appealing enough to engage diverse participants and clearly communicate the value they offer.

Amira's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Amira learns about the library makerspace from a colleague in the municipality's sustainability office. She's intrigued - not because she wants to make something herself, but because she sees potential in how such spaces can embody public values around reuse, resilience, and shared knowledge. She schedules a visit to observe one of the repair workshops.

ELECT

During her visit, Amira strikes up a conversation with the library coordinator and learns that the space is seeking broader recognition and support. She proposes a pilot project that links the makerspace with the city's circular education program. Her role is not operational but strategic: she helps define shared objectives, draft partnership terms, and embed evaluation tools.

EVALUATE

As the project unfolds, Amira checks in regularly. She collects data, speaks with facilitators, and joins occasional public events. While she sometimes finds it challenging to translate policy language into grassroots action, she learns from the community's hands-on logic. The space, in turn, benefits from clearer strategic framing and better documentation.

ENTRUST

Amira becomes an informal advisor to the space. She helps position it within city-wide strategies, connects it to funders, and supports the co-development of a public report on social impact. She doesn't lead from the front, but her influence shapes long-term sustainability and visibility.

Steffen

(they/them)

circularity expert

materials researcher

"If we can turn agricultural waste into high-quality textiles, we're not just making clothes—we're reshaping the system."

Residence: Potsdam, Germany
Age range: 37 -45 y.o.
Role/attitude: Circularity Expert / Sustainable Materials Researcher

background

Steffen works at the intersection of sustainability, fashion, and agriculture. They are a professional researcher or practitioner with expertise in circularity, aiming to connect industries that traditionally don't overlap. Their main focus is exploring how agricultural by-products (like hemp, flax, or other natural waste materials) can be transformed into new yarns, textiles, and fibers for sustainable fashion. They live an environmentally conscious lifestyle, are deeply embedded in sustainability networks, and are motivated by creating systemic change rather than just individual projects.

goal

Experiment, exchange with other experts and disseminate sustainable textile solutions from agricultural waste.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Familiar through events and collaborations but not a frequent hands-on user.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Expert-level knowledge of circular systems and material reuse.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Strong understanding of sustainable fashion but limited hands-on craft skills

behaviour

In the makerspace, Steffen uses the facilities for material experimentation and prototyping: testing fibers spun from agricultural waste, trying out small-scale textile production processes, and experimenting with blending natural and recycled materials. They also share their expertise by hosting talks or collaborative sessions to connect designers, makers, and agricultural stakeholders. They are less focused on personal DIY projects and more on developing scalable, innovative methods that can influence industries.

needs

- Access to advanced textile tools and prototyping machines (e.g., spinning, weaving, 3D textile printers).
- A platform to collaborate with m-a-t project, designers, farmers, producers, crafters, material scientists and consumers.
- Spaces to experiment with unconventional raw materials (agricultural waste, natural fibers, etc.).
- Documentation and testing support for turning experiments into scalable, reproducible methods.
- A community interested to engage with sustainable innovation and systemic impact.

barriers

- Funding and resource constraints for material research and testing.
- Bridging knowledge gaps on material innovation between fashion professionals and producers/consumers.
- Resistance in the market and industry to adopt new materials and processes.

Steffen's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Steffen hears about the makerspace through an academic partner. Their work focuses on turning agricultural waste into fibers. They're looking for a place to explore the potential of their innovative materials with designers and producers/craftpeople. When they visit the space, it's modest - but open-minded and full of energy. They notice the maker area and ask about whether it's possible to test experimental fabrics and materials or host material swaps.

ELECT

With cautious optimism, Steffen proposes a lab pop-up focused on co-designing with waste. They bring their own microscopes, dried fibers, and basic spinning tools. The event attracts eco-curious youth, craft lovers, and even a farmer interested in agri-waste production. It's messy, iterative, and full of exchange - not just materials, but ideas.

EVALUATE

Despite the success, Steffen notes the infrastructural limitations. No fume hoods, few specialized tools, and tight scheduling. Yet, the community's responsiveness is energizing. Through informal feedback, they learn that people want more: deeper engagement with agri-waste production/materials, local material literacy, and long-term residencies.

ENTRUST

Steffen co-authors a proposal for a permanent 'materials corner' inside the space. They host talks, advise on equipment procurement, and open pathways for collaboration between rural producers and urban makers. Their role becomes a hinge between experimental science and community-based learning.

Alina

(she/her)

crafter

student

“I want to make things that people love — and that don’t harm the planet.”

Residence: Kyiv, Ukraine
Age range: 20–21 y.o.
Role/attitude: University student, aspiring craft and fashion entrepreneur

background

Alina, 21, is a university student in Kyiv studying cultural studies. She spends much of her free time doing crafts, upcycling, and small-scale fashion design. She dreams of launching her own small brand of sustainable accessories and clothing. While she often works from home, the library and its makerspace have become important for her as a creative environment and a place to learn new techniques and connect with like-minded people.

goal

To develop her skills in craft and design, expand her creative network, and gradually prepare to launch her own small business in sustainable fashion.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Alina is learning sewing machines, laser cutters, and 3D printers, seeking ways digital tools can enhance her handmade designs.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Highly motivated, she experiments with recycled materials and upcycled fabrics, inspired by zero-waste principles to promote conscious consumption in her future brand.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Highly engaged, she’s passionate about fashion and crafts, follows trends, attends workshops, and shares her creative process online.

behaviour

Alina regularly visits the library to work on her designs, sew prototypes, and use shared equipment that she doesn’t have at home. She values the makerspace for its tools, learning opportunities, and community. She also uses the library to research design trends, business strategies, and sustainable production methods. From time to time, she participates in workshops or peer sessions to expand her network and gain new skills.

needs

- Access to quality crafting and prototyping equipment (sewing machines, laser cutters, textile printing).
- Mentorship or training sessions in entrepreneurship, design, and sustainability.
- A supportive community of makers and creative peers.
- A workspace that balances inspiration and functionality — calm enough for focus, yet alive with creative energy.

barriers

- Limited technical experience with digital tools.
- Few business contacts and little experience in self-promotion.
- Difficulty accessing equipment during peak hours.
- Balancing university studies with creative projects.

Alina's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

While scrolling through a student Telegram channel, Alina sees a post from the library about a beginner workshop on combining sewing with laser cutting. Curious, she decides to visit the makerspace. What she finds surprises her - not only is the space equipped with tools she's been dreaming of using (like textile printers and 3D printers), but it also feels open, inclusive, and youth-friendly. She's shy at first but sees other young people making things, and slowly begins to feel she belongs. The possibility to prototype her own designs and meet other creative students sparks ideas about what her brand could become. She's excited but aware she still lacks some technical skills and business experience.

ELECT

Encouraged by the vibe and the access to tools, Alina begins spending more time at the library. She signs up for open lab sessions and starts working on her first real prototype collection using scrap fabrics and laser-etched designs. She also joins peer-led events and meets other young women working on similar ideas. Sharing her progress online, she receives positive feedback and is motivated to keep learning. She starts asking the staff about how to organize a small exhibition or pop-up to test her products. Meanwhile, she juggles university deadlines and makerspace time - sometimes staying late or coming during quiet hours to secure a free machine.

EVALUATE

After a few months, Alina has produced several samples and received input from peers and mentors she met in the space. However, she's realizing the limits: the makerspace is often booked, some equipment is harder to use alone, and she still lacks guidance on topics like pricing, branding, or sustainable sourcing. She looks to the toolkit and online resources from other make-a-thek libraries, hoping to replicate some best practices or connect with external mentors. Despite the challenges, she feels her confidence growing - especially when others in the space ask her for advice or compliment her work.

ENTRUST

Alina starts hosting informal skill-sharing sessions at the makerspace, especially on combining handmade and digital techniques. She mentors a few younger students and applies for a micro-grant to develop her brand identity. The library becomes more than a workspace - it's her testing ground and a place where creative goals feel achievable. She collaborates with other users to co-design an open fashion event, showcasing circular fashion projects by young makers. While she still has a long way to go before launching her business, Alina feels that make-a-thek has given her a head start - and a community to grow with.

Irene

(she/her)

crafter

educational tutor

“I want to make things that feel like me, not just buy them.”

Residence: Milan, Italy
Age range: 29 y.o.
Role/attitude: Educational tutor and administrative assistant, weekend crafter of ceramic jewelry

background

Irene is a 29-year-old administrative assistant and educational tutor based in Milan. Over the weekends, she fully immerses herself in her true passion: crafting. Possibly, with leftover materials. Over the past few years, Irene has developed a personal line of handmade ceramic jewelry selling pieces occasionally at local art fairs and weekend markets. Her work is deeply intuitive and emotionally expressive, shaped more by curiosity and digital techniques/material experimentation than by formal training.

behaviour

Irene primarily engages with maker spaces during open lab weekends, on the advice of a colleague, as her full-time job limits her availability during the week. She is drawn to informal, welcoming atmospheres, where skills are shared in a non-competitive and friendly way. Rather than structured tutorials, she prefers learning-by-doing, experimenting with materials in a hands-on, intuitive manner. Her creative process is strongly influenced by visual inspiration, particularly through social media platforms like Instagram and Pinterest, where she also connects with other crafters

goal

exploring new materials and techniques and learning basic tools that could improve the way she produce and presents her creations; gain visibility for her handmade jewelry to sell more and be able to purchase new tools and materials

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

No experience, but willing to learn basic tools

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

No structured experience; attracted to reuse and low-waste practices intuitively, especially through upcycling and repurposing of materials.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Small personal experiments with jewelry and clay; sells handmade creations occasionally at weekend markets or fairs. Passionate but informal.

needs

- A flexible and accessible space for weekend use
- Informal, low-pressure environment
- Entry-level access to digital tools
- Peer-to-peer knowledge exchange
- Inspiration and networking through local events
- Opportunities to test and grow skills at her own pace

barriers

- Limited time availability due to full-time job
- Low confidence in using digital tools or fabrication machines
- Lack of professional equipment at home
- Discomfort in highly technical or overly professionalized environments
- Difficulty in finding clear, beginner-friendly information, hands-on training and peer learning experiences

Irene's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Irene works full-time as an administrative assistant at a local university. On weekends, she transforms into a crafter - creating handmade ceramic jewelry that she sells at small community markets and seasonal fairs.

While browsing social media for new techniques, she comes across a post about an upcoming 'Ceramic Meet-Up' hosted at the local library she usually attend. Intrigued by the idea of connecting with others who share her passion, she decides to check it out.

ELECT

At the event, Irene is pleasantly surprised. The space is welcoming, the people friendly, and the tools - like a basic kiln and jewelry-making tools - spark her curiosity. Although she doesn't consider herself a 'maker' in the tech sense, she sees potential in the space for her craft.

She signs up for an open lab evening and brings a few of her unfinished clay pieces to work on. She finds it refreshing to work outside her home, especially with others around.

EVALUATE

As weeks go by, Irene becomes a regular at weekend sessions. She begins testing new materials and exchanging tips with other users. She learns how to digitize simple logos for packaging using a vinyl cutter and joins a workshop on storytelling for handmade products. While she sometimes feels unsure about using more technical equipment, the staff is supportive and the vibe non-judgmental. Scheduling remains a challenge - weekday openings don't align with her job - but she adapts.

ENTRUST

Irene proposes a monthly peer meet-up for part-time crafters. She helps co-design a market-themed event hosted by the library, where members can display and sell their creations. She also starts occasionally mentoring others who are just getting started. Without fully realizing it, Irene has become a connector - bridging informal making with community and visibility.

Alicia

(she/her)

maker

teacher

“I have so many ideas in my head! if only I had the space and tools to bring them to life”

Residence: Helsinki, Finland

Age range: 30-40

Role/attitude: Educator, passionate hobbyist, and curious innovator

background

Alicia is a high school art teacher who loves blending art, technology, and play. While her small apartment restricts her ability to fully explore creative projects, the library makerspace provides the space and tools she needs to experiment. She uses it both to test ideas for her classes and to pursue her personal creative passions. For Alicia, making is a form of self-expression, problem-solving, and community building. Her strong interest in sustainability informs her reuse practices, and she frequently adapts what she learns to inspire her students and peers.

goal

Gain practical skills and confidence to create sustainable, circular fashion designs.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Experienced and self-taught

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Highly experienced in creative reuse and motivated by sustainable practices.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Skilled in crafts from leading student workshops.

behaviour

Alicia visits the makerspace weekly, staying for long sessions when she can. She uses a mix of tools - 3D printers, sewing machines, laser cutters, and Arduino kits- and attends workshops to expand her skills. She often steps into a mentor role, sharing what she learns with students, younger makers, and peers. Alicia relies on both digital resources (CAD software, online tutorials) and physical equipment, treating the makerspace as her creative bubble.

Occasionally, she also brings in her students when the library hosts special sessions for school groups—turning the makerspace into an extension of her teaching.

needs

- Access to advanced tools unavailable at home
- Affordable materials and supplies
- Workshops & structured learning pathways
- A flexible and collaborative workspace
- Technical support staff to troubleshoot equipment
- A community network to exchange ideas and find collaborators
- Opportunities to showcase projects to the public
- Pre-defined workshops or guided sessions tailored for visiting groups, where specific skills or tools are clearly demonstrated and explained

barriers

- Intimidated by digital components (CAD, coding, electronics)
- Broken equipment or technical maintenance
- Where to source materials and costs
- Time conflicts with work and makerspace's opening hours
- Uneven skill levels in workshops (too basic or too advanced)
- Cultural perception of making as “just a hobby”

Alicia's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Alicia first hears about the library's new creative space through a colleague. She visits during an open day, intrigued by the mix of analog and digital tools. She walks through the space slowly, imagining how her students could benefit from an environment that combines making, sustainability, and cultural heritage.

A short presentation about textile upcycling sparks her curiosity - she's never tried these techniques herself but sees the potential for hands-on, project-based learning.

ELECT

Inspired, Alicia decides to sign up for an after-school workshop. She begins experimenting with sewing machines and recycled materials in her spare time.

Encouraged by the friendly facilitators, she asks if she can bring a small group of her students to explore together. She collaborates with the library to co-create a pilot session combining textile craft and storytelling, tapping into local traditions and sustainability themes.

EVALUATE

The pilot goes well - students are engaged, and Alicia finds joy in working side-by-side with them in a new environment. She begins reflecting on how to integrate these experiences into her teaching practice more regularly. She encounters some limitations, like needing more structured guidance on digital tools or access to materials in bulk. Still, she feels the space is responsive and values her input.

ENTRUST

Over time, Alicia becomes a trusted contributor. She proposes monthly co-teaching sessions with other educators, invites fellow teachers to visit, and participates in planning meetings. She's no longer just a user - she helps shape the educational potential of the space, bridging school and library worlds.

Ramon

(he/him)

maker

product designer

*"Ideas are my materials,
and the makerspace is
my playground."*

Residence:	Barcelona, Spain
Age range:	28–40 y.o.
Role/attitude:	Professional maker, designer, and community collaborator

background

Ramon is a 34-year-old product designer from Barcelona, combining traditional craftsmanship with digital fabrication. He is recognized for his workshops on sustainable design and collaborates with universities, studios, and local associations. Active in local creative networks, he regularly participates in exhibitions, repair cafés, and skill-sharing events. He has strong expertise in design and making, but limited experience in fashion.

goal

To advance his professional practice in terms of skills and portfolio while mentoring others and contributing to community-driven design projects.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Expert in 3D printing, laser cutting, vinyl cutting, CNC milling, digital embroidery, and sewing technologies.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Designs with sustainability in mind, frequently repurposing materials and teaching reuse strategies.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Limited experience in fashion; focus is on product design and crafts.

behaviour

He uses the makerspace as a dynamic environment for creation, learning, and collaboration. He leads workshops, mentors other makers, develops community-focused projects, and uses the space for prototyping and small-scale production. The makerspace allows him to exchange knowledge with peers, explore new practices, and connect with the wider creative community.

needs

- To have flexible spaces for workshops and prototyping.
- To collaborate and network with peers.
- To gain visibility within the creative community.

barriers

- Limited resources for long-term projects
- Bureaucratic hurdles in organizing projects.
- Lack of fully equipped or dedicated spaces.
- Difficulty integrating active makerspace activities into quiet library environments.
- Understand how and when keep his activities into a different setting.

Ramon's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Ramon first learns about the library's creative space through a local event. He's curious but cautious - his previous experience with public spaces was often marked by underfunded, underused rooms. Yet when he visits, he finds a space that, while modest in equipment, buzzes with grassroots energy. Flyers about workshops and community projects cover the walls. He sees potential - not just for himself, but for nurturing local eco-design culture.

ELECT

Ramon approaches the library team and offers to host a one-off prototyping workshop. He proposes a session on creating sustainable home objects using recycled materials. With minimal bureaucracy and enthusiastic support from staff, he sets a date and gets access to basic tools. He even brings his own soldering kit and cutting mats. The session draws in curious locals, students, and even a couple of retirees with crafting experience. Even if take account of logistic activities (prepare the space, The room feels alive, collaborative, and open to improvisation.

EVALUATE

After the first session, Ramon receives positive feedback. Participants were engaged, asked for more sessions, and suggested collaboration ideas. However, he notes some friction: limited equipment, no budget for materials, and lack of long-term planning make it hard to scale. Still, he senses something important: the space is becoming a micro-lab for experimentation, and he's ready to invest time if there's vision.

ENTRUST

Ramon gradually becomes a core collaborator. He's not just running workshops but helping shape the future of the space. He mentors young designers, co-develops a local materials library, and helps pitch a joint grant with the library for mobile making kits. His presence ensures the space stays grounded in both creativity and sustainability.

Matteo

(he/him)

maker

startupper

"Sharing is caring"

Residence: Milan
Age range: 37 y.o.
Role/attitude: experienced maker, product designer, start-up founder

background

Matteo is the founder of a digital fabrication studio and design service that explores the intersection of technology, sustainability, and craft. With a background in product and interaction design, he has extensive experience working with 3D printing, CNC machining, electronics, open-source tools, and parametric design. He collaborates with both public and private stakeholders, focusing on education, co-design, and circular practices. He is driven by the idea of social impact through design, and is interested in public makerspaces as places of accessible innovation, experimentation, and local transformation.

goal

Encourage citizens and designers to adopt circular thinking using accessible tools and expand knowledge-sharing among maker and designer networks.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Expert in prototyping and advanced digital workflows.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Promotes sustainable production and collective learning.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Combines traditional techniques with product design.

behaviour

Matteo engages with makerspaces as a facilitator, educator, and project partner rather than a casual user. He brings structured expertise and designs workshops, objects, or small-scale productions with institutions. Hands-on and curious, he adapts his methods to audience and context. In public library makerspaces, he would contribute by offering training, co-developing learning pathways, or helping design modular setups that balance creativity and feasibility. He values collaboration but expects clear communication, flexibility, and basic readiness (tools, space, staff support) to engage meaningfully.

needs

- Access to public platforms and spaces that can host community-oriented circular projects.
- Shared access to machines and materials in non-commercial spaces (like libraries).
- Be part of training and mentoring programmes within public-facing contexts.
- Reliable co-design processes to activate citizens and stakeholders.
- Tools to map local actors and existing material flows.
- A space to be hosted to share projects and experimentations with talks and events.
- Places where experimentation is allowed to remain open, non-hierarchical, and iterative.
- Institutional support for community projects

barriers

- Misalignment between institutional logic and the fluidity of bottom-up, experimental design.
- Bureaucratic limits when working with public institutions.
- Difficulty in sustaining long-term engagement with fragmented communities.
- Lack of public spaces equipped for experimenting and sharing bottom-up ideas
- Circular practices perceived as "extra" instead of systemic.
- Limited funding for community projects

Matteo's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Matteo hears about the make-a-thek initiative through his collaboration with local institutions in Milan. He's immediately intrigued by the idea of placing circular making inside a public library - an everyday space that could shift narratives around reuse, learning, and materiality. He look at the toolkit, appreciating its modularity and the mix of digital and physical resources. It aligns with his way of working: open, iterative, and grounded in community needs. What excites him most is the potential for hybrid learning environments where hands-on experimentation meets public service.

ELECT

Seeing the opportunity, Matteo connects with a local library team to co-develop a concept around material reuse and public learning. He proposes a series of public workshops tied to existing maker tools, combined with open talks on local materials and urban mining. He suggests starting with a low-barrier session on 3D printing using recycled filament and simple open-source models, inviting participants to experiment with small everyday objects and customization. He brings his community of designers and makers into the space, inviting them donate wasted filament and supports librarians in shaping the event with easy language and open invitations.

EVALUATE

After a few sessions, Matteo evaluates what worked: strong participation, curiosity from unexpected user groups, and energy around material storytelling. However, he also encounters limitations: some machines aren't available or accessible in the library; library staff struggle to support more technical aspects; documentation is lacking. He begins co-writing a short how-to with the librarians and proposes integrating a materials library to enhance the space's value for future activities.

ENTRUST

Encouraged by the response, Matteo helps co-develop a more permanent space within the library - integrating knowledge-sharing, maker tools, and exhibition modules. He begins mentoring young users and offers feedback to refine the make-a-thek proect based on his field experience. His start-up and the library now co-host an annual circularity event, building bridges between creative professionals and public institutions. For Matteo, this becomes a new kind of infrastructure: collaborative, open, and embedded in civic life.

Marco

(he/him)

maker

self-taught

*“Paper, ink, and noise.
That’s all I need.”*

Residence: Reykjavík, Iceland

Age range: 23 y.o.

Role/attitude: DIY maker, punk scene enthusiast

background

Marco grew up surrounded by the DIY punk culture, where music, zines, and self-made objects shape everyday life. He learned serigraphy, collage, and analog printing by experimenting with friends and sharing tools in informal spaces. For Marco, making is more about community and expression than polished outcomes. His free time is filled with concerts, underground events, and long nights spent producing zines with fellow creators.

goal

Keep the DIY punk spirit active by producing, sharing, and connecting people through analog creativity.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Minimal digital skills; relies on friends for editing and final steps.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Deeply engaged in DIY punk networks, values reuse and collective making.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Strong analog practice: zines, serigraphy, collage, and hand-drawn work.

behaviour

Marco is driven by the energy of collaboration. He enjoys collective making sessions, where everyone contributes with simple tools and ideas. He tends to avoid digital complexity, preferring hands-on, messy processes that carry imperfections as part of their charm. When a project requires digital finishing, he openly relies on trusted friends, reinforcing bonds of mutual support. His commitment is less about building professional skills and more about keeping the DIY spirit alive — through events, zines, and workshops that spread the punk ethos of accessibility and independence.

needs

- Affordable access to printing and analog tools
- Spaces for collective making and sharing
- Support to document and preserve DIY practices
- Occasions to connect music, art, and making

barriers

- Limited digital skills and independence
- Few institutional spaces for underground culture
- Financial struggles to keep projects alive
- Lack of recognition of DIY as cultural value

Marco's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Marco hears about the Make-a-thek programme during a public talk on inclusive design. The idea of a makerspace inside a library intrigues him - especially one that's open to the public and rooted in community values.

He browse the m-a-t toolkit and feel inspired by the possibility to mix graphics, narrative, politics, and making. Yet, questions emerge: Will this space allow for radical experimentation? Is there room for irony, critique, subculture?

He take time to reflect, reading through case studies, and begin sketching ideas. Something about the openness of the toolkit makes him feel like this could be a place to play with formats, test new educational models, and break some traditional design rules, with others.

ELECT

Intrigued, he contacts the makerspace team, proposing a pilot workshop called "Print Your Protest", a simple risograph zine and T-shirt lab using local stories and found materials. They pitch it not just as a creative session, but as a way to activate dialogue and visibility for underrepresented voices.

The library team is supportive, but logistics are slow. He finds himself juggling bureaucratic steps, tool access issues, and the need to build relationships from scratch. Still, he reach out to local youth workers and activist groups to co-design the first event, to create a shared space for visual dissent.

EVALUATE

The workshop takes place on a grey and cold Saturday afternoon. Not a huge crowd, but enough to feel something shift. A teenager prints a slogan about housing rights. A mother and daughter stencil matching symbols on tote bags. The energy is raw, unpolished, but alive.

He documents everything about results and process though photos and videos, and asks participants what they'd like to do next. He learn that people want more than a one-off event: they want continuity, space to experiment, and a place to belong.

ENTRUST

After the first experience, he keeps showing up. Not always as a workshop lead: sometimes just hanging around, talking to new users, suggesting zine ideas, prototyping print stations or visual identity experiments with the library team.

He begin developing a loose visual language for the makerspace, one that users can remix - like a toolkit of symbols, colours, and slogans anyone can adopt.

He also mentors a younger participant who wants to launch a community digital group through the space. It feels like the beginning of a new practice: not just design for the public, but design with the public. The library is no longer a place to deliver content - it becomes a space of distributed authorship.

Emre

(he/him)

prosumer

engineer student

“The real test of understanding is being able to teach it to someone else.”

Residence: Berlin, Germany

Age range: 26 y.o.

Role/attitude: Master student of mechanical engineer

background

Emre is from Turkey and moved to Germany three years ago for his Master’s studies. He’s always been a creative soul, constantly making things and sharing ideas with others—he even built an open-source software project back home. He is very active on social media, with a YouTube channel where he reviews softwares and hardwares. Now he’s settling into his new life in Germany, exploring neighborhood activities and using them as a fun way to practice his German and connect with people.

goal

He wants to engage with local creative opportunities and, ideally, contribute with his skills.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Confident and curious in using and learning new technologies, especially if open-source.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Emre takes sustainability into account in his work (like optimizing models and using software efficiently), but is not an expert in that.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Emre doesn't have experience in this area.

behaviour

During this semester, Emre has an exam that requires him to design, 3D model, and print a few pieces. Since the university is far from his apartment and it's often very crowded, he decides to explore his neighborhood and discovers a makerspace at the local library. Excited by the opportunity, he sees it as a playground for experimentation and is eager to explore all its features. He even considers creating tutorials or reviews to share on his YouTube channel with his remote community. When he learns that the library also hosts workshops, he sees them as the perfect chance to practice his German, to connect with like-minded people, and maybe even to make new friends.

needs

- Access to local makerspace to work at his project
- Opportunities to practice German in a social setting
- Ways to keep sharing content with his online community
- Guidance and flexibility on how to use this specific makerspace

barriers

- Limited free time, busy academic and personal schedule
- Limited German skills, making some activities intimidating
- Unsure how to contribute his expertise to the library or local community
- Lots of other options in the city to meet communities
- Restrictive library regulations, such as limitations on taking photos and videos

Emre's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Emre discovers a library's makerspace in his neighborhood while searching for alternatives to his crowded university facilities. He explores the available equipment, workshops, and community activities to understand what the space offers and how it can support him this semester.

He evaluates how the makerspace could also serve as a place to have social interactions and practice German, as well as an opportunity to create content for his YouTube channel

ELECT

Excited by the possibilities, Emre decides to use the makerspace for his 3D modeling and printing project.

He registers, checks the schedules, and plans his visits, balancing his coursework with exploration of workshops. Beyond his professional and personal goals, he sees the makerspace as an opportunity to propose himself as a collaborator/expert for future workshops.

EVALUATE

Emre begins using the makerspace, testing different machines, software, and materials. The flexibility of it during working hours is something he appreciates a lot. He attends some workshops, interacting with staff and participants, making new friends, and practicing the language.

Meantime, his channel gained popularity, and the management of the library bought some professional equipment and asked him to co-create and share some content.

ENTRUST

Confident in his ability to navigate the makerspace, Emre incorporates it into his regular workflow. He continues to attend workshops, connect with other makers, and experiment with new techniques. He also proposes a series of talks on open source and actively contributes with some articles to the toolkit. He keeps sharing his experiences online, building a small community around his tutorials while deepening local connections, positioning the library as both a practical resource and a social hub for personal creations.

Marcos

(he/him)

citizen

Library user

“Time is short, so I focus on what matters: study, ideas, and the right connections.”

Residence: Helsinki, Finland
Age range: 40–45 y.o.
Role/attitude: Philosophy student, former engineer

background

Marcos, 43, moved from Chile to Helsinki to pursue a master’s degree in philosophy after working several years as a mechanical engineer. His shift from a technical to a humanistic field reflects a desire to focus on meaning, ideas, and critical thinking. He spends long hours in the library, which he values primarily as a quiet, concentrated study space.

goal

To have uninterrupted study time in a calm, quiet environment.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Technical background from engineering, but no personal interest in digital fabrication.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

General awareness; not a personal focus.

FASHION & CRAFTS

No direct involvement or interest.

behaviour

Marcos spends most of his time in the library immersed in philosophy study and research. He actively avoids the makerspace, seeing its activities and noise as disruptive to the quiet environment he depends on. He structures his time carefully to make steady progress in his studies, while selectively connecting with peers who share his academic interests.

needs

- Guaranteed access to silent and dedicated study spaces.
- Clear separation between study areas and makerspace activities.
- Transparent communication about when and how noisier activities take place.
- Reassurance that core library services (study, lending, access to information) remain intact.

barriers

- Noise from machines or group activities could disrupt his study routine.
- Possible competition for spaces between traditional users and makerspace participants.
- Fear that the library atmosphere might change, losing its focus on quiet reflection.
- Perception that makerspace activities are far removed from his personal and academic interests.

Marcos' Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Marcos has recently transitioned from a career in mechanical engineering to pursue a Master's in philosophy. This shift wasn't casual: it marks a conscious decision to focus on meaning, thought, and reflection. He chooses the library as his primary place of study for its quiet, structured atmosphere - something he deeply values - and more appropriate for him than an University Library. One afternoon, he notices a new poster near the entrance promoting the library's makerspace. While curious at first, he quickly dismisses it. The visual language and tone feel too far removed from his world - noisy, hands-on, fragmented. Not what he came for.

ELECT

Weeks later, Marcos finds the library unusually busy. A school group is visiting the makerspace, and the buzz spills into the main reading area. He's visibly irritated and moves to a quieter corner. While relocating, he walks past the makerspace and sees students working with textile scraps and discussing the philosophy of reuse. A facilitator mentions how making can also be a form of critical reflection. The idea lingers, but he does not act. He returns to his quiet reading room, noting the distraction - but also something intriguing in how ideas were being enacted, not just read.

EVALUATE

Marcos continues to study at the library, though he grows increasingly aware of the subtle changes in its ecosystem. Occasionally, makerspace activities are audible; posters and digital screens promote workshops and co-creation labs. He begins to question whether the library can still serve as a space for quiet, focused thought. At the same time, he reflects on whether his resistance comes from discomfort or from a deeper fear of being displaced by a model of learning he doesn't recognize.

ENTRUST

Eventually, Marcos responds to an open invitation to join a dialogue circle between library users and makerspace facilitators. He shares his concerns about noise, identity, and purpose. In return, he hears others speak about inclusion, material thinking, and learning through doing. While he doesn't plan to use the machines, he advocates for the coexistence of quiet and making. Marcos contributes to shaping a set of shared "library coexistence principles," helping define respectful zoning, noise levels, and visibility practices. Without becoming a maker, he becomes part of the governance - ensuring that the library remains a place for all modes of thought.

Jan

(he/him)

citizen

library non user

“I want to make things that feel like me, not just buy them.”

Residence: Prague, Czech Republic

Age range: 17 - 19

Role/attitude: student

background

Jan is a 17-year-old from Prague who spends most of his time skating around the city with friends. Skateboarding shapes not only his free time but also his style and identity. He loves skate fashion and has started personalizing his clothes, experimenting with small DIY changes. Although he hasn't been to a library in years, he is curious and quick to learn when technology and self-expression are involved.

goal

To explore and shape his identity by connecting personal interests with creative expression and peer experiences.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

No experience

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Reworks old clothes casually; not focused on sustainability.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Small experiments with customizing garments; strong personal interest in skate fashion.

behaviour

Jan would approach the makerspace as a place to explore creativity connected to his lifestyle. He would be excited to design and customize t-shirts, try sewing machines and heat presses, or experiment with digital tools like vinyl cutters. At the same time, he would use the space informally - hanging out with friends, doing schoolwork, or discovering new technologies in a playful and informal way. Because skating often damages his clothes, Jan could also be drawn to repair-focused activities, seeing mending not only as useful but as a way to creatively personalise his worn garments.

needs

- To experience activities as social opportunities, ideally with friends.
- To access short, targeted learning moments.
- To build practical skills through hands-on activities.
- To use technologies and tools for free that are otherwise unavailable at home.

barriers

- To perceive the library as a boring place only dedicated to studying and books.
- To lose motivation when peers of his own age are not engaged.
- To miss opportunities due to ineffective communication channels.
- To feel that the library is not welcoming to someone from a street culture background, leading to a sense of not belonging.

Jan's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Jan often hangs around the library after school. One day he notices a sign for a 'Custom Your T-shirt' session and drops in out of curiosity. Inside, he sees vinyl cutters, a heat press, and young people customizing old clothes with slogans and symbols. He's hooked. The vibe feels chill - not like school or youth centres. No one is talking down to him, and he's invited to try. He's also aware that customising and upcycling second-hand clothing is becoming a trend among people his age, which makes the experience feel timely and relevant.

ELECT

Jan returns the next week, this time bringing a couple of friends. They create matching patches and post their creations online. For the first time, he feels the library is offering something relevant, fun, and expressive. He starts chatting more with the staff, asking about other tools, and suggesting ideas like a music playlist or events after 5pm. He came for the creative side, but realises he can also use the space to fix up clothes ruined while skating - in a way that still feels personal and cool.

EVALUATE

Over time, Jan notices some friction. His friends don't always come back, and the space isn't always open when he's free. Some instructions feel too formal, and there aren't many people his age in leadership roles. Still, he keeps returning - it's one of the few spaces where he can be creative without pressure.

ENTRUST

Recognizing his engagement, the library invites Jan to co-design a youth event. He helps shape the format, promotes it on his socials, and even DJs during the opening. He's not just a user anymore - he's an ambassador for making in his own style and on his own terms.

Adriana

(she/her)

citizen

library non user

"If we meet, share, and create together, no one has to feel invisible."

Residence: Milan, Italy
Age range: 65+
Role/attitude: Retired, social activist

background

Adriana is a retired woman from Milan, part of local community group promoting social inclusion. She organizes workshops where sewing, embroidery, and knitting connect participants from diverse backgrounds, foster intergenerational learning, and give visibility to often overlooked skills. She sees the library as a social hub and safe space where relationships and community ties are built.

goal

To foster social inclusion and intergenerational learning through shared creative activities.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

No experience

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Basic awareness of sustainability and reuse principles, but little hands-on practice.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Basic knowledge in fashion; Interest in traditional crafts and strong skills in community facilitation.

behaviour

Adriana uses the makerspace as a social and educational platform, encouraging participants from all backgrounds - including older adults, migrants, and other vulnerable groups - to share skills and learn from each other. She facilitates workshops where traditional techniques are taught alongside modern methods like digital fabrication. Her focus is on fostering social connections, empowerment, and inclusion, rather than only mastering new technologies.

needs

- To create opportunities for skill and knowledge exchange across diverse groups.
- To communicate clearly and accessibly with participants of all backgrounds.
- To have resources for turning informal gatherings into structured, visible community programs.
- Trust from the library management and the community itself.

barriers

- To lack technical expertise for facilitating workshops.
- To miss participants due to ineffective communication.
- To encounter inaccessible spaces or tools.

Adriana's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Adriana is a long-time resident of the neighborhood. She hears about the makerspace through a friend who attends a knitting circle. Curious, she visits during a community open day. She sees young people screen printing in one corner and elders sewing in another. The space is lively, diverse, and more energetic than she expected.

ELECT

She decides to stay. With encouragement from the staff, she proposes leading a weekly embroidery session. The library provides a small budget for materials and helps promote it. Participants come from diverse backgrounds - some seeking connection, others practical skills. Adriana welcomes them all with warmth and patience.

EVALUATE

Over the weeks, Adriana learns to adapt. She introduces simple patterns for beginners and lets more advanced participants take initiative. While she doesn't use the digital tools, she partners with younger facilitators to bridge analog and digital approaches. The experience reminds her of why she loved teaching: the shared joy of learning.

ENTRUST

Adriana becomes a pillar of the space. She helps develop intergenerational programming, advises on accessibility, and ensures new users feel welcome. Through her, the makerspace becomes a site not only of creation, but of care and community repair. Her role naturally evolves into someone who facilitates, inspires, and amplifies others - more than just a user. She embodies a profile that could carry a visible "facilitator" badge in the system.

Elena

(she/her)

citizen

library - non user

“Art gives me energy, but I need places that make it easy to reconnect with it.”

Residence: Budapest, Hungary
Age range: 42 y.o.
Role/attitude: Accountant, mother, art enthusiast

background

Elena is a 42-year-old accountant and mother of two children, aged 10 and 12. Though she studied economics, she has always been passionate about art, museums, and creative expression. Many of her clients work in creative or freelance fields, keeping her loosely connected to the cultural world she admires. She enjoys reading and attending exhibitions, but her full-time job and parental responsibilities leave little time for herself. She often wishes for activities that can either include her children or run in parallel, so she doesn't have to choose between parenting and creative pursuits.

goal

To reconnect with her passion for art in ways that are accessible, efficient, and compatible with her role as a mother.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

No experience.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

Basic awareness from cultural interests, but no hands-on practice.

FASHION & CRAFTS

No specific craft practice, but strong appreciation for cultural and artistic value.

behaviour

Elena noticed a flyer at the library about a creative workshop and decided to join. Initially hesitant, she was drawn in by the cultural angle of the event. She prefers low-tech, hands-on activities with artistic elements - particularly those she can attend without committing to long courses.

When the makerspace offers family-friendly sessions or simple parallel activities for her children, she feels more comfortable and engaged. Over time, she becomes a returning participant, occasionally bringing her kids along when the context allows.

needs

- Practical, low-threshold activities that don't require prior digital skills
- Flexible formats (e.g. one-off events, drop-in sessions) that fit a busy family schedule
- Possibility to engage her children in parallel creative activities or child-friendly versions of the workshops
- Clear and inviting communication through both digital and analog channels (posters, flyers, local press)

barriers

- Lack of time to commit to long-term or regular programs
- Risk of perceiving the makerspace as too technical or “not for her”
- Perception that the library is not a space designed for families with older children
- Bureaucratic or complex access (online bookings, mandatory registration)
- Communication gaps if events are promoted only online

Elena's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Elena stops by the library on a Saturday morning with her 12-year-old daughter. While returning some books, she notices a flyer for an upcoming creative workshop on textile printing and circular design. The fact that the event is hosted in a cultural space she already trusts piques her interest. The flyer mentions it's beginner-friendly and welcomes families. She smiles. It's rare to find something that speaks to both her artistic curiosity and her life as a mother. That evening, she visits the library's website and finds more info: short sessions, no experience required, and even a kids' corner for parallel activities. It feels like someone finally designed something with her in mind. She registers online, even if the platform is a bit clunky, hoping this could be the start of something she's been missing.

ELECT

On the day of the event, Elena brings both children. A staff member greets them warmly and shows them around the space. Her kids settle into a simple hands-on activity in the adjacent room, while Elena joins the workshop. She's nervous: she hasn't done anything creative in years, but the atmosphere is casual, welcoming, and non-judgmental. She tries her hand at stamping fabric and talks to other participants. Some are parents too, and this sense of shared time, without pressure, feels energising. After the session, she chats with the facilitator and learns there will be more events like this. She leaves with a handmade tote bag and a spark she hasn't felt in a while.

EVALUATE

In the following days, Elena keeps thinking about the workshop. She reflects on what worked: the short format, the supportive environment, and the fact that her children were engaged nearby. She'd love more regular events but worries about time and communication: she doesn't always check emails or the website. She stops by the library to suggest that future events be advertised via flyers in schools or posted on local Facebook groups. She also expresses interest in joining again and maybe bringing another parent-friend. The experience made her realise that creativity doesn't have to wait until the kids are older: it can be shared.

ENTRUST

A few months later, Elena is a familiar face at the library's creative sessions. She brings her daughter regularly, and sometimes her son joins too. She's become an informal advocate, suggesting new ideas to the team and even helping spread the word in her neighbourhood. While she's not leading anything herself, she's a bridge: between parents and programming, between the library and families seeking meaningful time together. The makerspace has become her space too. Somewhere that doesn't ask her to choose between roles, but allows her to combine them creatively.

Olena

(she/her)

citizen

library non user

“The library and makerspace are my place to connect with people and do something useful for my family.”

Residence: Kyiv, Ukraine
Age range: 35+ y.o.
Role/attitude: Service worker, seamstress and knitter, internally displaced person

background

Olena, 37, is a mother of two children (ages 7 and 12) and an internally displaced person who moved to Kyiv from Kostyantynivka (Luhansk region) due to the war. She works in the service industry and has skills in sewing and knitting. The library and makerspace have become important social spaces for her — places where she can meet people, find support, and use available resources to repair or create clothes for her children without major expenses.

behaviour

Olena visits the library and makerspace regularly to repair clothes, knit for her children, and spend time with others. She values the chance to learn new techniques and build a sense of belonging in her new city. She often seeks advice from more experienced users and takes on practical projects that bring immediate benefits to her family.

goal

To access resources and knowledge for making and repairing clothes, while also finding community and social connection in a new environment.

needs

- Access to equipment for sewing and repairs.
- Practical workshops on sewing, knitting, and basic crafts.
- Opportunities for communication and peer support.
- Safe, affordable access to materials and tools.

DIGITAL FABRICATION LITERACY

Basic level – Olena is skilled in manual techniques such as sewing and knitting. She finds digital makerspace tools interesting as additional support for repairs or simple projects.

CIRCULARITY & REUSE

High level of practical application – she frequently repairs and repurposes clothing for her children, saving resources and reducing expenses.

FASHION & CRAFTS

Moderate – she uses her skills for practical family needs rather than following fashion trends, yet sees crafting as a form of self-expression and creativity.

barriers

- Limited financial resources for materials.
- Small social network after relocation.
- Needs guidance when using digital tools.
- Balancing work, childcare, and craft time.

Olena's Journey

pre

during

post

EXAMINE

Soon after moving to Kyiv, Olena learns from a neighbor that the local library has a makerspace open to the public. Curious and looking for ways to adapt to her new life, she visits with her younger child one afternoon. She's surprised to find sewing machines available and a cozy area where people are knitting and working on small repairs. At first, she hesitates - unsure if she belongs in such a space - but the atmosphere is friendly and someone offers to show her how the machines work. For Olena, this small gesture is key: the space becomes a door not just to tools, but to connection.

ELECT

Encouraged, Olena starts visiting the makerspace regularly, using it to mend clothes for her children and make small practical items like scarves and mittens. She joins a basic sewing workshop, where she feels reassured by seeing other women - some also displaced - working on similar projects. Over time, she builds the confidence to ask questions and try new techniques. The opportunity to create something useful, save money, and speak with people in a safe and warm environment becomes a vital part of her weekly routine.

EVALUATE

As Olena becomes more familiar with the space, she starts helping others who are less experienced with sewing, sharing tips and small tricks she learned from her mother. She's interested in learning more about the digital tools (like the embroidery machine or fabric printer) but finds them intimidating without guidance. She's also aware that materials can be expensive or hard to come by, so she tries to reuse everything she can. Occasionally, she suggests ideas to staff: like running a second-hand fabric exchange, or creating a WhatsApp group to stay in touch with other users. These small steps make her feel more involved and appreciated.

ENTRUST

Over time, Olena becomes a familiar face in the makerspace. She is seen as approachable and generous, especially by new users. The staff occasionally ask her to help during workshops, or to speak about her experience as part of outreach efforts. While she doesn't see herself as an expert, she realizes how valuable her presence is to others. For Olena, the library is no longer just a place to mend clothes - it is a lifeline: a space where she feels useful, connected, and able to give something back to the community that welcomed her.

5. Conclusions and Outlook

The research presented demonstrates the value of **grounding service and space design in the lived experiences, needs, and aspirations** of diverse users and professionals across the pilot library ecosystems. By developing a broad and differentiated set of user personas and user journeys, the project not only captured the complexity of local contexts but also illuminated shared patterns, values, and barriers that cut across geographies and roles.

A key insight that emerged throughout the process is the evolving role of libraries. In several cases the *make-a-thek* exploration became an opportunity to reframe the identity of the public library - not only as a service provider, but as a hybrid civic space for creative experimentation, community resilience, and informal learning. **This shift in mindset among librarians and stakeholders was itself a transformative outcome of the research.**

Looking ahead, the personas and journeys developed here will serve as a strategic foundation for the next phases of the project. They will directly inform the design of the modular *make-a-thek* toolkit (WP4), supporting decision-making around space planning, activity formats, and support materials tailored to real users' needs. Moreover, they will help set expectations and minimum requirements for participating libraries, guiding implementation in a flexible but grounded way.

Design Guidance from Personas and Journeys

The personas and user journeys developed in this task are not static deliverables, but **strategic tools** that will actively inform and guide the ongoing design and implementation of the *make-a-thek* approach. They allow the consortium to maintain a **user-centred perspective** throughout all phases of the project, ensuring that the makerspace solutions - both physical and digital - are grounded in the real experiences, motivations, and barriers of diverse users.

In particular, they will be used to:

- **Inform the design of the *make-a-thek* modular toolkit** (T4.2–T4.3), ensuring it addresses the needs and capacities of different user types and library contexts.
- **Define entry points, support levels, and communication strategies** tailored to specific profiles (e.g., librarians with low technical confidence, or citizens new to circularity).

- **Guide the creation of learning and facilitation resources** in WP5, by identifying where skill-building is most needed and how different users approach experimentation.
- **Support the spatial and service design of the pilots** (WP7), by identifying key moments, frictions, and enablers in the user experience within the physical space.
- **Contribute to community engagement and sustainability strategies** (WP6, WP8), by mapping motivations for participation and long-term involvement.
- **Evaluate the impact of the *make-a-thek* approach**, offering baseline scenarios and behavioural patterns that can be compared to real use cases in later stages (WP11).

Ultimately, these personas and journeys help shift the focus from “*what the space provides*” to “***what people need and experience***”, **ensuring that the *make-a-thek* becomes a meaningful, inclusive, and sustainable infrastructure for learning, making, and circular innovation.**

Beyond the immediate project, these tools can continue to **support reflection and alignment among stakeholders - offering a shared language** to discuss who the *make-a-thek* spaces are for, what kinds of experiences they enable, and what support systems are needed to make them inclusive, relevant, and sustainable.

